

A Study of Antifertility Agents : 47-Synthesis of 4-Aminoalkylisocoumarins[†]

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Synthesis and antifertility activity of some 4-aminoalkylisocoumarins and antifertility activity of some known analogs of leonurine are reported. Compound 22 elicited antifertility activity in rats at 5 mg/kg dose.

DEVELOPMENT of non-toxic luteolytic agent that would have a minimal interference with the reproductive cycle is perhaps an ideal approach towards the control of fertility. Based on the structure of a potent luteolytic agent leonurine, isolated from *Leonurus sibiricus*¹, the present study describes the synthesis and antifertility activity of

4-aminoalkylisocoumarin derivatives, which may be considered as closed chain analogs of leonurine and the antifertility of some of the known compounds² in which the guanidine chain of leonurine was substituted with other bases.

Synthesis of 4-alkylisocoumarin was carried out following the Scheme 1. The reaction of bromoacetone with substituted benzoic acid (1-5) in methanol-water in the presence of K_2CO_3 furnished the corresponding acetonyl derivatives^{3,4} (6-8). No acetonyl derivative was formed from 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid and 3,5-dimethoxy-4-hydroxybenzoic acid because of the free phenolic group.

Leonurine

Scheme 1

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Cyclisation^a of acetyl 3,5-dimethoxybenzoate (6) by keeping it in 85% H₂SO₄ yielded 4-methyl-5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (9). Under the above cyclisation condition, acetyl 3-methoxybenzoate (7) gave an inseparable mixture of 4-methyl-5-methoxyisocoumarin (10) and 4-methyl-7-methoxyisocoumarin (11), which were characterised on the basis of their pmr spectra, δ (CCl₄) 2.05 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.08 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.20 (1H, s, C-3-H), 2.22 (1H, s, C-3-H), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 6.70-7.60 (6H, m, Ar-H). The acetyl derivative of 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzoic acid surprisingly failed to undergo cyclisation on PPA or concentrated H₂SO₄ treatment.

Bromination reaction of 9 with *N*-bromosuccinimide in dry carbon tetrachloride in the presence of catalytic amount of benzoyl peroxide gave 4-bromomethyl-5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (12) which when treated with appropriate bases gave the desired isocoumarins (13-15). Hydrogenation of the above isocoumarin bases in the presence of 10% Pd-C at 50 psi furnished the corresponding dihydroisocoumarins (16-18). 4-Methyl-5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin was found to be very unstable on silica gel or basic alumina and all the compounds were, therefore, purified by repeated crystallisation.

Experimental

The melting points were determined in an electrically heated block (Townson & Mercer, Croyden, England) or in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. All the compounds were checked routinely for their structure by extensive use of spectroscopy. The ir spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer 157 and 177 spectrophotometers. The pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60D and R-32 spectrometers using TMS as internal standard. The chemical shift values are expressed in δ and *J* value in Hz. The mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol-JMS-D 300 instrument. The purity of the compounds was routinely checked by silica gel G or basic alumina tlc plates.

Typical examples of preparation of compounds are given below.

4-(Pyrrolidinobutyl)-3,4,5-trimethoxybenzoate (24) : A mixture of 20 (1 g, 7.0 mmol) and 21 (1.6 g, 7.0 mmol) in pyridine (10 ml) was kept for 17 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured onto ice-water; extracted with ethyl acetate, washed with water, dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated. Excess of pyridine was removed under vacuum and the residue purified by column chromatography over basic alumina, using benzene as eluent to give 24 as a free base which was converted into its hydrochloride salt (70%), m.p. 124-6° (lit.⁵ 127°).

Similarly, 4-(diethylaminoethyl)-3,4,5-trimethoxybenzoate (22), m.p. 152°^a and 4-(diethylaminobutyl)-3,4,5-trimethoxybenzoate (23), m.p. 138-39°^r were

prepared from diethylamino ethanol (19, *n*=2) and diethylamino butanol (19, *n*=4), respectively.

5,7-Dimethoxy-4-methylisocoumarin (9) : A mixture of 6 (2 g, 8.4 mmol) and H₂SO₄ (28 ml, 85%), was kept at room temperature for 3 h when slowly a dark-green colour developed. On adding crushed ice to the reaction mixture, 9 was obtained as a solid (1.5 g, 83%). It was crystallised from ethanol to yield the product (70%), m.p. 175° (lit.⁸ 175-76°).

5,7-Dimethoxy-4-bromomethylisocoumarin (12) : A solution of 9 (1 g, 4.54 mmol), *N*-bromosuccinimide (1 g, 5.6 mmol) and benzoyl peroxide (0.01 g, 0.04 mmol) in dry carbon tetrachloride (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 h, cooled, and succinimide formed was filtered off and the filtrate concentrated. A solid material thus obtained was chromatographed on silica gel using benzene as eluent. After concentration of the solvent, the residue was crystallised from chloroform-hexane to yield the product (0.8 g, 58%), m.p. 170-80° (Found: C, 48.35; H, 3.98. C₁₂H₁₁BrO₄ requires C, 48.16; H, 3.37%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1555, 1605 and 1720 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.95 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.35 (1H, s, OCH=C), 4.7 (2H, s, CH₂Br), 6.82 (1H, d, C-6-H, *J*_m 2Hz) and 7.38 (1H, d, C-8-H, *J*_m 2Hz).

5,7-Dimethoxy-4-(*N*-diethylamino)methylisocoumarin (13) : A solution of 12 (2 g, 6.66 mmol), pyrrolidine (1.1 ml, 15.4 mmol) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (2.5 g) in dry benzene (40 ml) was refluxed for 4-5 h, cooled, filtered, diluted with benzene, washed with water, dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated to give 13 as a solid material (1.8 g, 94%) which was converted into its hydrochloride salt. Repeated crystallisation from dry ethanol-ether furnished colourless crystalline product (0.8 g, 45%), m.p. 186° (HCl) (Found: C, 58.85; H, 6.83; N, 3.99. C₁₆H₂₁NO₄.HCl requires C, 58.62; H, 6.71; N, 4.27%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1580, 1600, 1665, 1720 (C=O) and 2950 cm⁻¹; δ (CCl₄) 0.98 (6H, t, 2×CH₂CH₃), 2.52 (4H, q, N-(CH₂)₂), 3.62 (2H, s, CH₂N), 3.72 (6H, s, 2×OCH₃), 4.18 (1H, s, C-3-H), 6.58 (1H, d, *J*_m 2Hz, C-6-H) and 7.18 (1H, d, *J*_m 2Hz, C-8-H).

Similarly, 5,7-dimethoxy-4-(*N*-pyrrolidino)methylisocoumarin (14) and 5,7-dimethoxy-4-(*N*-morpholino)methylisocoumarin (15) were also prepared from 12: yield 46%, m.p. 213° (HCl); and yield 50%, m.p. 227° (HCl), respectively.

5,7-Dimethoxy-4-(*N*-diethylamino)methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (16) : A solution of 13 (0.1 g, 0.34 mmol) in methanol (25 ml) and Pd-C (10%, 50 mg) was hydrogenated on Parr hydrogenator at 50 psi for 6 h. The catalyst was filtered off and the solvent concentrated to give 16 as an oil (0.07 g, 70%) (Found: C, 65.38; H, 7.48; N, 4.44. C₁₆H₂₃NO₄ requires C, 65.32; H, 7.85; N, 4.77%); ν_{\max} (neat): 1500, 1605 and 1720 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 0.95 (6H, t, N-(CH₂CH₃)₂), 2.1-2.7 (6H, m, -CH₂-N-(CH₂)₂), 4.6-4.85 (1H, m, C-4-H), 6.5 (1H, d, *J*_m 2Hz, C-6-H) and 7.04 (1H, d, *J*_m 2Hz, C-8-H): *M*⁺, *m/z* 293.

Similarly, 5,7-dimethoxy-4-(*N*-pyrrolidino)methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (**17**) and 5,7-dimethoxy-4-(*N*-morpholino)methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (**18**) were also obtained as oils from **14** and **15** : yield 80 and 75%, respectively.

Biological activity : All the compounds were tested for their antifertility activity in female albino rats in the Endocrinology Division of this Institute following the method described earlier⁸. Compound **22** was found to be active at 5 mg/kg ; all other compounds were found to be inactive at 10 mg/kg dose.

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